

Studying the antibacterial activity of iron oxide nanozymes against *Escherichia coli*

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ABSTRACT:

Iron oxide nanozymes are tiny substances that resemble enzymes and are being researched for their capacity to fight bacterial infections because of their efficacy and durability. This study examined the antibacterial properties of iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) nanozymes against the common gut bacterium *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). The ability of the nanozymes to stop bacterial growth was examined after they were created using chemical co-precipitation. The concentration was 1 mg/mL, and antibacterial effectiveness was determined using agar plate tests. At this concentration, Fe_3O_4 nanozymes were found to successfully kill *E. coli* cells. Fe_3O_4 nanozymes can limit bacterial growth at low doses, according to recent research. Additional research, such as minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) assays, is needed to establish the minimal effective dose required to inhibit or kill *E. coli*. This study emphasizes the potential of iron oxide nanozymes as efficient antibacterial agents, paving the path for further research into their broader applications in bacterial illness management.

Keywords: Iron oxide nanozymes, *Escherichia coli*, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, antibacterial

1. INTRODUCTION:

Nanozymes are a type of synthetic enzyme; their significance as enzyme analogues stems from their capacity to catalyze reactions that are comparable to or on the same level as their biological counterparts (Wei and Wang, 2008). These nanoparticles have sparked widespread interest, particularly in biomedical and environmental domains (Gao & Yan, 2016). They have features and activities similar to natural enzymes, but with added benefits such as stability in harsh circumstances and inexpensive production costs (Zhang et al., 2018). Nanozymes have been utilized to limit bacterial growth, reduce biofilm formation, and detect biological and environmental analytes (Mei et al., 2021).

Additionally, gold, silver, and carbon-based nanomaterials have been incorporated into a composite matrix to improve catalytic capabilities and display enzyme-like activity/behavior

(Dhiman et al., 2022). The stability, affordability, and catalytic activity of iron oxide nanozymes, such as Fe₃O₄ and γ -Fe₂O₃, have drawn a lot of interest, especially in physiological settings (Attar et al., 2018). According to Gao et al. (2017), these iron oxide nanozymes imitate the activities of catalase and peroxidase, depending on pH. According to Wei and Wang (2013), peroxidase-like nanozymes effectively lower bacterial loads by interacting with cell membranes and blocking bacterial DNA and other molecular processes to produce reactive oxygen species like hydroxyl radicals. Additionally, biofilms, which are bacterial networks, can be modified by Fe₃O₄ nanozymes (Gao & Yan, 2016).

In 2007, researchers reported the first use of iron oxide nanozymes, demonstrating their peroxidase-like activity (Gao et al., 2007). These nanozymes were obviously suitable for application in antibacterial treatments since they catalyzed the conversion of hydrogen peroxide into hydroxyl radicals at physiological pH (Zhang et al., 2022). The mechanism of this iron oxide nanozyme is similar to that of natural peroxidases, such as horseradish peroxidase, in that it oxidizes organic substrates through a ping-pong reaction in which H₂O₂ cleavage produces Reactive Oxygen species (ROS) (Gao et al., 2007). The objective of the present investigation is to evaluate iron oxide nanozymes' antibacterial efficacy against *Escherichia coli*.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Requirements:

1. **Glassware:** 100 ml conical flasks, 100 ml beaker, glass stirrer, petri dish, Agar plates, 5 ml measuring cylinder, 50 ml measuring cylinder, slides,
2. **Chemicals:** Gram's decolorizer (ethyl alcohol), Safranin, oil immersion, crystal violet stain (gentian violet), Gram's iodine
3. **Media:** Sterile Mueller Hinton agar & sterile Nutrient broth
4. **Culture:** 18 hrs old culture of *E.coli* MTCC 1302
5. **Instrument/Equipment:**
 - a. Autoclave
 - b. Bacteriological Incubator
 - c. Weighing balance
 - d. Optical compound microscope
 - e. UV-Visible Spectrophotometer

6. Miscellaneous:

Cotton, gloves, lab coat, newspaper, rubber bands, tissue, 70% ethanol, nichrome wire loop, pipette, Forceps, Calibration weight set of known masses (500mg, 200mg, 100mg, and 20mg), staining rack, sterile pipette tips.

2.2 Method for Fe₃O₄ Nanozyme synthesis:

1. Ferric chloride aqueous solution and ferrous chloride aqueous solution were mixed thoroughly on a magnetic stirrer.
2. NaOH was added dropwise until a black precipitate was obtained.
3. The obtained precipitate was washed and neutralized by centrifugation.
4. The resulting Fe₃O₄ colloidal particles obtained were dried and characterized further with a UV-visible spectrophotometer.

Fig 1: Synthesis of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles through Chemical Co-precipitation Method (Wulandari et al., 2018)

2.3 Media Preparation and Sterilization:

Preparation and sterilization of bacteriological media

Mueller Hinton agar (2 plates of 20 ml each)

$$38g = 1000ml$$

$$x = 40ml$$

Therefore 1.52 g of *Mueller Hinton agar* /40ml

1. Nutrient broth (2 tubes of 2.5 ml each)

$$13g = 1000ml$$

$$x = 5ml$$

Therefore 0.065 g of *Nutrient broth* /5ml

2. Saline (20 ml)

It is 0.85%

$$0.85g = 1000ml$$

$$x = 20ml$$

Therefore 0.17 g of Nacl /ml

Fig 2 : Saline solution (left), Mueller Hinton agar (right), and nutrient broth (center) prepared for autoclave.

Fig 3: Media sterilization in Autoclave at 121°C /20min

2.4 Agar well diffusion assay to assess the antibacterial activity of synthesized Fe₃O₄ Nanozymes:

2.4.1 Inoculation of *E. coli*

1. Begin with a master plate containing the *E. coli* culture.

2. Using a sterile nichrome wire loop, inoculate the *E. coli* from the master plate into a liquid medium (nutrient broth)
3. Incubate the culture for 18 hours at 37°C with shaking at 350 RPM.

$$A = \epsilon \cdot c \cdot l$$

The 18-hour culture was enumerated for the number of bacterial cells using the equation: At 600 nm

$$1 \text{ OD} = 8 \times 10^8 \text{ cells/ml}$$

Measuring Optical Density (OD)

According to the CLSI (Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute) guidelines, for antibacterial assays, a sample's bacterial concentration should range from

$$1 \times 10^6 \text{ cells/ml} - 1 \times 10^8 \text{ cells/mL}$$

2.4.2 Spectroscopy Setup and Measurement:

1. Begin by turning on the UV-Vis spectrophotometer and allowing the lamp to warm for 20 min/ according to the manufacturer's guidelines. Next, calibrate the instrument using a blank solution (solvent without nanozymes) to set the baseline to zero.
2. For measurement, place the nanozyme sample in a quartz cuvette and insert it into the spectrophotometer. Set the wavelength range from 200 nm to 800 nm to capture the full UV-visible spectrum of the sample.

2.4.3 Antibacterial Assay Setup

Agar plates:

1. Prepare sterile agar plates for the antibacterial assay.
2. Wells were bored in the agar using a sterile borer, ensuring equal spacing and size for consistency.
3. 100 µl culture was spread on the agar plate.
4. A 100µl (NZ) sample was added to the wells.

Incubation and Observation

1. Incubate the plates at 37°C for 24 hours to allow for bacterial growth.
2. Following incubation, observe the plates for zones of inhibition around the wells containing antibacterial agents.

2.5 Ethical Considerations and Safety Concerns

1. Use of Biological Agents:

The study involved handling *Escherichia coli*, a live bacterial strain. Standard biosafety protocols were strictly followed to minimize risks of contamination and ensure the safety of personnel. *E. coli* used in this experiment is a non-pathogenic strain, and its use complies with institutional guidelines for microbiological studies.

2. Nanozyme Safety:

Iron oxide nanozymes are nanoparticles that may pose potential health risks, particularly through inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact. Proper safety measures, such as wearing gloves, lab coats, and face masks, were followed during the synthesis, handling, and disposal of nanozymes. Fume hoods were used to avoid any unintended exposure to nanoparticles.

3. Environmental Impact:

Nanoparticles can have environmental implications if not disposed of properly. All waste materials, including nanozyme solutions and bacterial cultures, were disposed of by environmental safety protocols to prevent contamination of water and soil.

4. Ethical Treatment of Data:

All data generated from the experiment were handled responsibly, ensuring accuracy, transparency, and honesty in reporting. There was no fabrication, falsification, or manipulation of results. Any limitations in the study design were acknowledged to maintain the integrity of the research.

5. Human and Animal Subjects:

The study did not involve any human or animal subjects, eliminating the need for ethical clearance related to human or animal testing.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

3.1 Analysis of the Nanozyme solution using UV-Vis spectrophotometer:

Fig 5: UV Spectra of Iron Oxide Nanozyme

The UV-Vis spectroscopy analysis revealed that the synthesized nanozymes are composed of iron oxide, based on the absorption peak observed between 359 nm and 377 nm. This absorption range corresponds with the known reference spectra for iron oxide nanoparticles, confirming their identity. The broad range of absorption (359-377 nm) is significant because it indicates that the size of the nanoparticles plays a crucial role in determining their spectral characteristics. In the case of iron oxide nanoparticles, smaller particles tend to absorb at shorter wavelengths (closer to 359 nm), while larger particles shift the absorption towards longer wavelengths (closer to 377 nm). This shift in wavelength is due to changes in the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) properties, which depend on particle size. Thus, the variation in peak wavelength within this range suggests that the synthesized nanozymes likely consist of nanoparticles with slightly varying sizes, contributing to their specific optical properties.

3.2 Antimicrobial Activity:

Fig 6: a. Antimicrobial Activity (indicated by arrow) of Iron Oxide Nanozymes b. Control (sterile Distilled water)

The study revealed significant antibacterial activity of the iron oxide nanozyme against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). A 23 mm zone of inhibition was observed, clearly indicating the ability of the nanozyme to prevent bacterial growth. This result suggests that the iron oxide nanozymes were effective in killing *E. coli* cells. The antibacterial effect is likely due to the nanozymes' ability to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), which damage bacterial cell walls and disrupt essential cellular functions, leading to cell death. Additionally, the small size of the nanozymes facilitates better interaction with bacterial cells, further contributing to their antibacterial properties.

In comparison, the control sample, treated with sterile distilled water, showed no zone of inhibition. The absence of a zone of inhibition in the sterile water control is attributed to the fact that sterile distilled water does not possess any antibacterial properties. As a neutral solvent, water cannot generate reactive species or interfere with bacterial cellular processes, thus allowing the bacteria to grow without restriction. This confirmed that the inhibition seen in the enzyme-treated sample was entirely due to the nanozyme itself, with no contribution from external factors.

3.3 Limitation of the Study: A key limitation of this study is that the effect of varying concentrations of iron oxide nanozymes on *E. coli* was not explored. The experiment was conducted using a single concentration of nanozyme, which, while showing significant antibacterial activity, does not provide a complete understanding of how different concentrations may influence bacterial inhibition. It is quite possible that a higher or lower concentration of the nanozyme could yield different results in terms of the size of the inhibition zone or overall effectiveness. Thus, the lack of concentration-dependent studies limits the ability to fully assess the optimal dosage or range of concentrations required for maximum antibacterial efficiency. Future studies should focus on exploring the antibacterial activity across multiple concentrations to better understand the dose-response relationship and refine the potential applications of iron oxide nanozymes.

4. CONCLUSION:

The antibacterial activity of the synthesized iron oxide Fe_3O_4 nanozymes is illustrative of the potential of Iron oxide nanozymes to inhibit bacterial growth. The concentration of nanozyme used herein was 1mg/mL, which is visibly killing the bacterial cells. The minimum effective concentration of Fe_3O_4 nanozymes that will inhibit and kill the *E.coli* needs to be determined

further by MIC and MBC-based assays. The minimum bactericidal concentration of Fe₃O₄ nanozymes against the test organism *E.coli* could be equal to or less than 1 mg/mL. For future studies, the focus should be on testing the antimicrobial activity of different concentrations of iron oxide nanozymes on various Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Additionally, comparative studies using different types of nanozymes against a single microorganism could provide insights into their relative efficiencies, helping to optimize nanozyme-based antibacterial treatments.

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